

STUDENTS READ BOOKS WITH THE HELP OF WORKS OF ART FACTORS OF INTEREST DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *Philosophical, pedagogical and psychological sources emphasize that the influence of various factors is significant in the development and socialization of a person. This article talks about the factors that influence the development of the child's personality and the importance of artistic ages in the meaningful organization of free time of young people.*

Key words: *reading, book, science, education, spirituality, educational institutions, fiction, classical literature, work, moral character, interpersonal relations.*

The following factors are important in the development of national character traits in a person:

1. Family environment (life of family members based on national culture and values, priority of national moral views in lifestyle, observance of Uzbek etiquette in interpersonal relations).
2. The presence of necessary conditions for the assimilation of national character traits in the microenvironment to which the child belongs.
3. Organization of interpersonal communication in educational institutions in accordance with national moral views and Uzbek rules of etiquette.
4. Compliance with the requirements of national ethics in the holidays, customs and ceremonies organized in the neighborhoods.
5. Compliance with the requirements of national-cultural ideas and national-ethical standards in social relations organized in labor teams and informal groups.
6. Attention is paid to the study of national history, culture and values in society.

7. Wide promotion of national history, culture and values among the population, including the youth, by mass media and social organizations.

It is known that most of the child's daily life is spent in the family environment. Therefore, it is important for the family to have conditions that allow the child to develop national character traits. "Character traits are formed based on the family environment, interpersonal relations, number of children, age difference, conflict situations and their appearance, parental attitude." In addition, "characteristics formed in early youth are extremely stable, and even making some changes to them is very difficult."

In the organization of family education, taking into account the age, psychological and personal characteristics of the child, introducing them to the essence of national traditions, ceremonies and holidays, with the characteristics of nationality and national character in the example of adults' behavior, behavior, interactions and relationships with others. focusing on close walking is considered pedagogically effective. "It is known that a child is imitative from a young age. Children tend to imitate their parents and other close people around them. They try to imitate adults' behavior, mannerisms, gestures, how they behave at the table, how they treat small children and their speech, even their tone of voice, in every detail. That is why, under the influence of the social environment, certain character traits in a child begin to strengthen from a very young age, as if they were formed by themselves. The characteristic of imitating adults is preserved even during the growth of children.

The microenvironment to which a child belongs also serves to develop national character traits in his personality. The national nature of children's games, the creative approach to their organization, as well as the fact that participants are required to have qualities such as activity, ingenuity, resourcefulness, and quickness in their actions, show their incomparable educational potential. Adults can directly and indirectly participate in the organization of national children's games with their

instructions and guidance. It is important for them to show the role and importance of children's national games, their main ideas, and character education. Pedagogical activity organized in this way in general secondary educational institutions serves as the next important stage for the development of national character traits in students. Interpersonal relations established in these institutions have a particularly educational effect. After all, with their help, "special features of the character" are created. Teams formed in educational institutions play a special role in strengthening the individual's will and moral character. "A person does not live alone, separated from each other, he lives in a certain community, for example, in a certain family, school, workshop, field. The team is the connecting link between the individual and the society. A person's activity, play, study and work takes place in this community. The team is not only the closest clear environment of the individual, but also educates the individual. The necessary positive features of a person's character can be brought up only in the community, and indeed they are brought up in the community.

Character traits such as "organization, discipline, orderliness, self-control, self-control, and self-demanding" are brought up in the team, which are important to be reflected in the image of each person. Being in close contact with members of the team "grows the skills and abilities of subordinating one's personal aspirations to the will of the team, and develops feelings of community - comradeship and friendship."

The role of the teachers of the educational institution, including the teacher of literature, in the development of national character traits in a person who is a typical representative of the community is particularly noticeable. Therefore, they "deliberately show people who can be an example to the student as an example to the child and the student; draws the student's attention to the actions and behaviors of this person and tells which of these actions are good, positive, and which are negative, bad. The educator looks for and implements tools that will help to

eliminate bad habits in the child's behavior and strengthen good, useful habits. The educational work also consists in the fact that the pedagogue should awaken the awareness of the necessity of self-emergence of certain positive qualities in the student's character and develop this awareness.

Studying examples of classical and modern Uzbek literature, evaluating their content and the impact of the proposed ideas on the development of national character traits in students showed that there are certain shortcomings in this regard. They will be discussed in detail below.

In classical and modern Uzbek literature, there is a small number of characters with characteristics of independence, independent thinking and independent decision-making in relation to existing situations. In many cases, one of the characteristics of a willful character - independent thinking and decision-making - is reflected only in the form of rulers, commanders or leaders. However, there are almost no works that express the character of independence in the character of ordinary people, especially young people, who are its typical representatives. Artistic heroes who are bright representatives of independent youth can be found only in historical works. For example, Oibek's novels "Navoi", Pirimkul Kadyrov's "Starry Nights" and the main characters of Maqsud Sheikhzoda's drama "Jalaluddin Manguberdi" - Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Jalaliddin Manguberdi show their ability to think independently and make decisions about existing situations. . This situation shows that all three heroes were statesmen, kings and sultans, their education was started from a young age, and special attention was paid to the development of spiritual, moral and willful qualities in them as individuals who follow the country. Means

Insufficient attention is paid to the portrayal of initiative persons, including young people, in the national literature. Only in some works, which are examples of children's literature, it is possible to observe that certain initiatives have been put forward to organize spiritual and educational events, to establish social activities

specific to students in the educational institution or outside it. In almost all of the artistic works about the life of teenagers, the initiative of young people is almost not visible. Works such as Olmas Umarbekov's "It's Hard to Be a Man" and Mirzakalon Ismaili's "Fergana at Dawn" talk about the active participation of young people, including students, in society. However, in these works, as in others, the role and influence of the Komsomol (Communist Youth Union) organization is recognized as a motivating force for youth social activity. In all the works created during the time of the former Union, special emphasis was placed on the leadership of this organization in ensuring the social activity of young people. After all, according to the policy of the totalitarian regime, it was necessary to cover the active participation of the Communist Party or the Komsomol organization in the life of the population and youth in every artistic work created on the national scale. During the years of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the socio-political views changed radically in terms of content and ideology. During the years of independence, many youth organizations were founded that united the youth of the republic. Today, these organizations and their ideological leadership role are evident in the lives and activities of young people. The large-scale social activities carried out by the organizations are a necessary condition for young people to get education, work, volunteer, and also fully demonstrate their talents and capabilities in various spheres of social life. - aimed at creating conditions.

Literary teachers working in educational institutions do not have sufficient experience of developing such characteristics of students through the use of artistic works that reflect the national lifestyle and character traits through the medium of fiction. A tradition has been followed in the practice of literature education for many years. According to this tradition, each topic is introduced in exactly the same format, that is, information about the author's life and work, as well as works of art presented as examples. Then the events reflected in them, positive and negative images, the idea and solution of the work are discussed. However, students do not

organize a deep analysis of the content of the works, evaluate the depicted events, express personal opinions, discuss the achievements of the authors, and the mistakes made, if any. This situation causes students to not develop the ability to think and analyze independently. Eliminating the above-mentioned shortcomings will allow effective development of national character traits in students.

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